

CMMR Lab™

COMPUTATIONAL MECHANICS
& MATERIALS RESEARCH

Thermomechanical Properties Of Polybenzoxazine Resin in a Molecular Dynamics Model as a Function of Degree of Cure and Temperature

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Outline

- **Motivation**

- **Background**

- **Objectives**

- **Methodologies**

- **Results**

- **Conclusions**

- **Acknowledgements**

What We Need

- **Advanced composites to reach space exploration milestones**
 - Extreme temperatures
 - Thermal protection
 - Lightweight materials
- **Manufacturing challenges**
 - Samples to useable parts
 - Process Modeling
 - Changing material properties

From <https://interestingengineering.com/transportation/what-keeps-spaceships-from-burning-up-during-reentry>

Other Materials Have desirable properties

- **Curing → Shrinkage**
- **Pyrolysis → Porosity**
- **This can create voids and initialize cracks**
- **Minimizing formation during processing can improve overall material properties**
- **Other materials have cure expansion**

Credit: NASA-Evaluation of Microcracking in Two Carbon-Fiber/Epoxy-Matrix Composite Cryogenic Tanks

³Savage, *Carbon-Carbon Composites* (1993)

Objectives

Virtual Curing Virtual Testing

Molecular Dynamics

Finite Element Analysis

Monomer

Molecular model

ΔT

Process-induced residual stress contours

Micro-scale finite element model

Accumulating stress

Failure

Fracture specimen

What We Can Do With Molecular Dynamics

- Perfect Microscope
 - DSC data
 - Tracers and diffusion
 - XRD
 - Mechanical Testing
 - Thermal properties
 - Chemical reactions
 - Spectroscopy
- ...At the same time!

LAMMPS stands for **L**arge-scale **A**tomic/**M**olecular **M**assively **P**arallel **S**imulator.

Polybenzoxazine (PBZ) Introduction

- **bisphenol-A aniline benzoxazine (BA-a) monomer**
 - Same reaction twice on both sides
 - Other PBZ precursors are also in use
- **Thermoset resin**
 - Ring opening homopolymerization, partially understood
 - “Ionically activated” / “thermally accelerated polymerization”
 - Evidence for autocatalyzation from polarized groups
- **Desirable properties**
 - **Little to no cure shrinkage, but why and how?**
 - Good mechanical properties
 - High glass transition temperature (Tg)
 - No byproducts

Gaikwad² et al., ACS Applied Polymer Materials 2021 3 (12), 6407-6415 DOI: 10.1021/acsapm.1c01164
Ishida et al., *Handbook of benzoxazine resins*: Elsevier, 2011, pp. 3-81.

Reaction Steps

Bisphenol-A
aniline PBZ

One side of
Bisphenol

May Receive
Bridge
(Used Ring)

Both Sites
Unused

Post
Reaction

May Open ring
(Used Ortho)

PBZ Density evolution

$$\text{Volume shrinkage} = \left(\frac{\rho_{\text{cured}}}{\rho_{\text{uncured}}} - 1 \right) * 100\%$$

Ishida³ et al., "A study on the volumetric expansion of benzoxazine-based phenolic resin," *Macromolecules*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 1099-1106, 1997

Modeling

- **Start with randomized monomer gas at 0.25 g/cc**
 - Monomer from Chemdraw
 - Randomized Replication in Python script 250 molecules: 16250 atoms
 - PCFF-IFF applied in LUNAR⁴ (with modified H- σ)
- **Repeat to make five 250 monomer replicates**
- **Densify to liquid density and Relax**
- **Cure using Reaction templates⁵**
- **Post cure Annealing**
- **Measure Properties**
- **Heat from 200K – 800K**

Kemppainen⁴ et al., "LUNAR: Automated Input Generation and Analysis for Reactive LAMMPS Simulations," 2024, doi: 10.26434/chemrxiv-2024-9tqz2.

Gissinger⁵ et al., "REACTER: A heuristic method for reactive molecular dynamics," *Macromolecules*, vol. 53, no. 22, pp.

Cured Models

- **Uncured Density Validation**
 - This study experimental 295K: 1.183 ± 0.024 g/cc
 - Simulated 300K: 1.184 ± 0.002 g/cc
- **Post Cure Density Comparison**
 - Experimental density [2] is the closest density at 1.182 g/cc, other literature values are higher.
 - Full Cure models at 1.173g/cc with best method
- **Closest method is the blue line**
 - Cluster evolution data every 1%
 - Density evolution every 5%
 - Tensile and CTE evolution every 10%

What is Free Volume

$$V_{System} = V_{Free} + V_{Atom}$$

- User Inputs:**
- voxel_size
 - **probe**radii
 - **vdw**radii

DETDA Monomer

Gsêê wêlunê ânâlÿsîş sêşulÿş
 Dênşîÿ
 Şînuâlâÿîon çêll wêlunê
 Atjôn wêlunê
 Gsêê wêlunê
 Rêşçênÿ Gsêê wêlunê

Atom Volume

PBZ Thermal and Cure Density Evolution

PBZ Thermal and Cure Atom Volume Evolution

$$V_{System} = V_{Free} + V_{Atom}$$

-- (dashed) System Volume
___ (solid) Atom Volume

PBZ Thermal and Cure Free Volume Evolution

$$V_{System} = V_{Free} + V_{Atom}$$

Summary

- **Cure shrinkage analysis using Free volume is Insightful**
 - More analysis possible using bond length and dihedral angle distributions
- **Residual Stress can be modulated with Temp and Cure rate**
- **More material Properties**
 - Tensile data in progress
 - Tg and CTE from same data
- **Future projects**
 - Improve Tg fitting
 - Study H-sigma effects
 - Modify PBZ FF parameters
 - PBZ variants

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- Cecil Evers (FSU)
- C3MD
- USCOMP

Thank you! Questions?

Regression Fringe Response Modulus Method

- Tensile simulations using class2-xe Force Field*
- Automated processing* of Stress-Strain data (QR code)
 1. Low pass filter of MD data
 2. Algorithm to determine linear elastic region
 3. Algorithm to find yield point
 4. Process full array of 3 directions-5 replicates-many DoC-many Temps
 5. Determine outliers

*Methodologies not published yet, 2 papers submitted

Mechanical Property Evolution

Independent variables

- 0%-90% cure
- 300k – 475K
- 3 directions, 5 replicates (mean and std of these)

Dependent variables

- Filter Cutoff Frequency
- Linear region / Young's Modulus
- Yield Stress / Yield Strain
- Poisson's ratio in transverse directions

No outliers removed Currently

- Negative Poisson's
- large Y intercept

Experimental: Modulus, 5.49 ± 0.33 GPa; Yield, 49.2 ± 2.02 MPa [2]

Modulus Data [MPa]

Cure:Temp	300K	325K	350K	375K	400K	425K	450K	475K
0%	1824.8	1112.8	1106.4	975.4	998.2	755.3	866.2	805.7
10%	2054.1	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	1019.6
20%	2058.1	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	1626.0
30%	2532.9	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	1355.7
40%	2751.7	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	1790.2
50%	2819.9	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	2038.2
60%	3221.2	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	2290.4
70%	3193.3	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	2542.2
80%	3689.8	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan	2909.6
90%	4074.2	3551.2	3743.8	3607.9	3902.8	3276.9	3196.2	3040.1

Mechanical Property Evolution

Mechanical property evolution

PBZ Glass Transition Evolution

- **Fit volume with hyperbola model**
 - Fit depends on range used
 - Top from 200K to 800K
 - Bottom uses -13C to 287C
- **Will further explore fitting methods**

PBZ Thermal and Cure Evolution

Free Volume with respect to Cure at many Temperatures

PBZ Thermal Expansion Simulations

- **Start with annealed models**
 - Every 10% cure
 - Five 16250 atom systems
- **Cool to 200K**
- **Relax for 1 ns**
- **Heat at 75K/ns**
 - Data files every 30K
 - Average density
 - Average energies
- **Fit volume with hyperbola model⁶**

Patrone⁶, P. N., et al. (2016). "Uncertainty quantification in molecular dynamics studies of the glass transition temperature." *Polymer* **87**: 246–259.

PBZ CTE Evolution

- **Fit volume with hyperbola model**
 - Fit depends on range used
 - Top from 200K to 800K
 - Bottom uses -13C to 287C
- **Will further explore fitting methods**
- **Find experimental source**

Reading Free Volume or Mechanical Property Plots

- **Points are average and standard dev. between runs**
- **x-axis for independent variable**
 - Temperature
 - Time
 - Degree of Cure
- **Color for 2nd independent variable**
 - Degree of Cure
 - Temperature
 - Processing Method
- **y-axis data from post process**
 - Density, Atom volume Free volume
 - Elastic modulus, yield, Poisson

PBZ Thermal and Cure Free Volume Evolution

Free Volume with respect to Temperature at many Cures

PBZ Thermal and Cure Evolution

EPON-862 Free Volume

Free Volume with Temperature at many Cures

Free Volume Evolution With and Without anneal

Gel Point Determination

- **Inflection point of largest cluster**
 - standard method for CMMR
- **Uses every 1% cure averaged between 5 replicates**
 - Standard deviation in mass at same DoC shown
- **Now fittable with constructed function**
 - Future work to finalize function choice, it may possibly become a sperate paper.
 - “Double Gaussian Turn” is shown and works well
- **PBZ is consistently just over 50%**
 - 53.2% for constant volume final run
 - 52.7% for constant pressure final run
 - ~51% in early testing
 - ~40% with reaction rate error

Final cure method data

- Cure NPT @475k: get density @475k, 50k/ns cool, 2ns NPT @300k get density
- Cure NVT @ 600k 1.185 g/cc: Hold 3ns NVT, NVT cool at 5k/ps, 1ns NPT @300k get density

NPT cure

NVT+3ns aniso relax

Final cure method data + Thermal cycle

- Cure NPT @475k: get density @475k, 50k/ns cool, 2ns NPT @300k get density
- annealed NVT (last slide) + 2ns NPT @475k, 50k/ns cool, 2ns NPT @300k get density

NPT cure

NVT+3ns aniso relax+NPT cycle

PBZ Cure cycle

Normal Cure cycle

